

Preparation and Characterisation of Tetrachlorobis-(4-t-butylphenoxy)tungsten(VI)

K. C. MALHOTRA, NEERAJ SHARMA*, RAJENDER SHARMA and S. C. CHAUDHRY

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh Univeristy, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

Manuscript received 11 January 1993, revised 11 August 1993, accepted 1 September 1993

Recently, the aryloxide chemistry of tungsten(vi) has been of interest since a few tungsten(vi) aryloxide complexes have been utilised as effective precursors for metathesis of olefins and are known to exhibit catalytic properties¹. Although W(OPh)₆ has been known for years², the synthesis of complexes W(OAr)_xCl_{6-x} with $x = 2, 3$ and 4 , using some substituted phenols has been described in recent years³, wherein it has been found that the number of chlorine atoms that may be substituted in WCl₆ is strongly dependent on the nature, the number and the position of the substituents on the aromatic ring of phenol. In view of these interesting observations and importance of tungsten complexes with phenoxide ligands, we report here the preparation and characterisation of [WCl₄(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₂].

Results and Discussion

WCl₄(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₂ (**1**) was prepared by reacting tungsten(vi) chloride and Me₃SiOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 in 1 : 2 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride. The elemental analysis of **1** are in good agreement with the proposed stoichiometry. The complex is a black solid with decomposition point 122°. It is soluble in common organic solvents and is a non-electrolyte. The cryoscopic molecular weight determination in nitrobenzene indicated it to be a monomer.

The ir spectrum of the complex shows that the ν_{CO} mode at 1180 cm⁻¹ in free Me₃SiOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 is at 1110 cm⁻¹ in the complex, consistent

with coordination through oxygen. This is further supported by the appearance of new bands at 545 and 535 cm⁻¹ assigned to the terminal ν_{W-O} mode⁴. Formation of dinuclear complex bridged through the aryloxo group was excluded because of the absence of any band due to ν_{W-O→W} which would appear much lower than terminal ν_{W-O} mode. The sharp bands at 370 and 345 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{W-Cl} mode⁵ (Table 1).

The ¹H nmr spectrum of **1** exhibits a singlet (t-butyl protons) at δ 1.26. The *o*- and *m*-phenoxy ring proton resonances (δ 7.08 and 7.33) in [WCl₄(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₂] are significantly shifted downfield compared to the free ligand resonances (δ 6.75 and 7.23) which support the formation of complex **1**. Thermal studies (DTA-TG) of compound **1** show that the compound is stable upto ~ 120°. Weight-loss of 53.4% in the first stage and 8.85% in the second stage have been rationalised in terms of the following reactions :

Here C₁₀H₁₃Cl stands for *p*-Cl.C₆H₄.C(CH₃)₃ or C₆H₅C(CH₃)₂CH₂Cl. An endothermic peak at 122.4° corresponds to the decomposition temperature of the compound while two exotherms at 322.5 and 542.5° may be attributed to the decomposition of the organic moiety C₁₀H₁₃Cl and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA FOR **1** AND ITS ADDITION COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Mol. wt Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	V _{W-O}	V _{W-Cl}	V _{W-N}
		W	Cl	C	H				
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂] ^a	650 (624)	29.3 (29.4)	22.8 (22.7)	38.1 (38.4)	4.0 (4.1)	2.5	545 535	370 345	-
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ (EtNH ₂)]	690 (669)	27.7 (27.5)	21.1 (21.2)	39.2 (39.4)	4.7 (4.9)	1.9	525 532	340	300
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ (Et ₂ NH)]	-	26.2 (26.4)	20.3 (20.4)	41.1 (41.3)	5.4 (5.3)	2.1	530	335	285
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ (Et ₃ N)]	740 (725)	25.5 (25.3)	19.7 (19.6)	-	-	1.8	520 528	345	292
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ (Pr ⁿ NH ₂)]	- (683)	27.1 (26.9)	21.2 (20.8)	-	-	2.0	535 540	330	290
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ (Bu ⁿ NH ₂)]	712 (696)	26.5 (26.4)	20.6 (20.4)	41.1 (41.3)	5.1 (5.3)	2.3	535 538	350	295
[WCl ₄ (OAr) ₂ .Bu ⁿ NH]	- (696)	26.2 (26.4)	20.6 (20.4)	-	-	2.2	530 535	365	298

^aC₆H₄Bu^t-4

the intermediate WO₂Cl₂, leading to the formation of WO₃ as the final residue. The tungsten content in the residue has been found to be consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the complex (**1**).

Based upon the analytical, thermal, ir and nmr spectral data it is proposed that complex **1** possesses an octahedral geometry which is supported by the earlier literature reports on similar compounds³.

The reactions of **1** with ethylamine, diethylamine, triethylamine, n-propylamine, n-butylamine and t-butylamine in equimolar ratio are slightly exothermic giving complexes of composition [WCl₄(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₂].Amine]. The elemental analyses of the adducts are in good agreement with the 1 : 1 stoichiometry (Table 1). They are hygroscopic, non-electrolytic and monomeric in nature. Coordination of the amine to tungsten is confirmed by the appearance of new bands around 280–300 cm^{-1} (W–N). The trends in the shifts of ν_{NH} , ν_{CN} and the H–N–C deformation mode are in agreement with the earlier reports on similar addition compounds with alkoxides and phenoxides⁶. It is therefore proposed that the complexes of **1** with amines form 1 : 1 addition compounds with a pentagonal bipyramidal arrangement around tungsten.

Experimental

WCl₆ (Fluka) (correct Cl analysis) was used as such. HOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 was used after recrystallisation from benzene. The amines were purified by literature methods. Me₃SiOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 was prepared by the reaction of HOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 with Me₃SiCl (1 : 1) in the presence of Et₃N.

[WCl₄(OC₆H₄Bu^t-4)₂] (**1**) : To a CCl₄ solution of WCl₆ (3 mmol) was added Me₃SiOC₆H₄Bu^t-4 (6 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h. The solution was filtered, the volatiles were removed by distillation and kept overnight. The resulting black solid was recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂ and dried under reduced pressure.

Reaction of complex (1) with amines : Complex **1** was mixed with an equimolar amount of amine in dry CCl₄ and the mixture was stirred for 12 h. The progress of the reaction was indicated by a colour change. The product was then isolated as a solid by concentrating the resulting solution followed by addition of hexane. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Tungsten was estimated by treating the complex with concentrated HNO₃ and then igniting to

WO₃ at 500°, Cl by Volhard's method and amines by steam distillation with alkali and titration of the distillate with H₂SO₄ using bromophenol blue. Oxidation state of tungsten was determined by treating the complex with a known excess of cerium(IV) sulphate solution and back-titration with iron(II) sulphate solution. C and H analyses were carried out on a Carlo Erba 1106 instrument. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Beckmann IR 4250 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a JEOL JNM PMX 60 S1 spectrometer using Me₄Si as internal standard. Thermal studies were carried out on a DTG-40 (simultaneous DTA/TG module Shimadzu) instrument. Conductivity of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complex in PhNO₂ was measured on an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge. Molecular weight was determined cryoscopically in PhNO₂ using a Beckmann thermometer.

References

1. F. QUIGNARD, L. LECONTE and J. M. BASSET, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1986, **36**, 13; H. HOCKER, R. MUSCH, F. R. JONES and I. LUEDERWALD, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1973, **12**, 430; H. R. DODD and K. J. RUTT, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1982, **15**, 103; 1985, **28**, 33.
2. H. FUNK and W. BAUMANN, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1937, **231**, 264.
3. F. QUIGNARD, M. LECONTE, J. M. BASSET, LEH YEH HSU, J. J. ALEXANDER and S. G. SHORE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 4272.
4. R. B. ROFF, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1956, **9**, 781.
5. D. M. ADAMS, J. CHATT, J. M. DAVIDSON and J. GARATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2189; K. W. BAGNALL, D. BROWN and J. G. H. CHIPRECH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2603.
6. H. J. BERNSTEIN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 161; J. E. STEWART, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **30**, 1259; L. K. DYALL and J. E. KEMP, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, **22**, 467; A. J. MORITZ, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1960, **16**, 1176.

